

Hermes2D soccer simulation TDP 2024

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Abstract. Soccer Simulation 2D is the main part of the RoboCup competition, where The Football 2D is simulated and code is written for them.

This paper is the technical report of the Hermes team, the team members are all 14 years old, and this year is the first year they want to participate in the Iran Open[3] and RoboCup competitions.

In this technical report, we want to present the ideas that we have given to improve the players' movements (shooting, passing, tackling, etc.).

Keywords: RoboCup, Soccer simulation, defense strategy.

1. Introduction

RoboCup[6] is an international scientific initiative that aims to improve the capabilities of intelligent robots. The goals of the 2D football simulation league are as follows. First is the development of simulators that form the infrastructure of the simulation system and simulate realistic phenomena prevailing in disasters. The second is the development of intelligent agents and robots that can play a role in disaster response scenarios. The Hermes team is going to participate in this competition for the first time in 2024. This team dedicated four months to learning programming with C++ language and then worked for 6 months on improving Base Agent algorithms. We are coding in StarterAgent[1]. So far, we have worked on defensive strategies such as marking and makeup, and in the future, we plan to improve shooting, passing, tackling, dribbling and defensive strategies in the base code.

We have read different Team Description Papers of different teams such as Yushan[7], Hades2D[5], HELIOS2023[2], etc and written this paper.

2. Defensive strategies

2.1 Block

Block will run at the time that the ball is in the hands of one of the opponent players and at that time, we will send the closest player to the opponent with the ball in its hands

to try and get the ball on its own. This strategy didn't work correctly at first but we're looking for a better solution to block the opponent.

2.2 Tackle

The idea we implemented to improve the tackle is that we made a condition using the `existKickableOpponent` function to confirm the presence of the opponent's kicker.

Then check the distance of all players (except the goalkeeper) to the ball with the `for` loop. Finally, compare the distance of the teammates with the player's own distance, and if the player was closer to the ball than his teammates and his energy was sufficient, we will order the player to go towards the ball and the opponent using `Body_GoToPoint`. Finally, we force the player to tackle with the `doTackle` function.

3. Offensive strategies

3.1 pass

To make the pass better, we have given some ideas that we will discuss below:

- First we checked the distance between the player and the teammate: The smaller the distance between the player and its teammate, the higher the score.
- We drew a circle around the teammate and checked if there is any opponent in that section.

Fig. 1. Circle around the teammate

- We drew a line between the player and its teammate and checked if there was an opponent in that line. If there was an opponent player on this line, we would deduct the points.

Fig. 2. line between player and teammate

- We measured player X and teammate X, and if teammate X was more than the player X, we added points.

3.2 dribble

In order to be able to dribble more accurately and find the best way to dribble, first the player who wants to dribble should draw a line to the goal, then check to see if there is a player on that line, and if there is no player, dribble, but if there is a player draw another line to the goal with a distance of 5 degrees from the initial line and check again to have the correct way to dribble. But according to game results this strategy didn't work correctly so we are looking for a better solution.

Fig. 3. Drawing lines to the goal to check and finally dribble

3.3 Shoot

In order to the player to know which side to shoot, first a line is defined with Vector2D as the size of the goal. Then we mark 14 points with intervals of 1 on the line we want to mark and draw a line to understand how the bal is going to go to from the player to each point. Then, according to the factors that we use to score each line and point, Such as the distance of the player to the point and the line, the distance of the goalkeeper to the point, the distance of the point to the sides of the goal, etc. Based on these factors, the player scores each point and, in the end, it is the point that exceeds everything.

Fig. 4. Draw a line from the player to the goal to choose the best shot path

Conclusion

This paper described the ideas and efforts and researches of the Hermes 2D[4] team. Defense algorithms allow us to choose the right position against player attacks. Also, attack algorithms help us score more goals against the opponent.

Future works

We have given ideas to improve the team's game so far, and for the future we want to: optimize the pass and dribble algorithm, make the goalkeeper smarter and add mark for defense. We want to work on more complex algorithms and get to know the base more. And try to make the pass and shoot and etc. action work better. And we want to participate in IranOpen and RoboCup competitions and compete with teams of the same level to make progress.

References

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